

Still no sign of the unnamed priestess?

Assessing Narrative Understanding with the FolkLURE Benchmark for the Narrative Domain

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Digital Humanities researchers increasingly rely on Large Language Models (LLMs) for analyses in their respective domains, such as cultural heritage, literary analysis, as well as text mining and knowledge extraction tasks. In this project, we are interested in investigating how much LLMs understand literature. We ask if ontologies, which have a long tradition of being used in narrative analysis, can be used to assess the performance of large language models on the fictional domain.

In recent studies, ontologies have been used to create interpretable benchmarks to test LLM capabilities in understanding, reasoning, and learning (Zhang et al. 2025). On the one hand performance of large language models is often impressive, even superhuman, in real-world domains, but for the fictional domain, which often does not follow the constraints of the real world, their performance still falls short, especially for long-tail knowledge (Graciotti et al. 2025). For example, an LLM may fail to recognize an unnamed priestess, who was murdered in Greek mythology, as a victim, showing the gap of LLM in narrative understanding, while the tale of a popular character such as Zeus is recounted without problems.

To address this, we draw on a range of hand-curated folkloristic and narrative ontologies, including the Aarne-Thompson-Uther Index (ATU-TMI; Declerck et al. 2017), the Morphology of the Folktale (Pannach 2021), and ontologies for fictional characters and events (Pianzola et al. 2025), alongside controlled vocabularies for narrative domains. Using these structured resources, we design an ontology-grounded question-answering (QA) task to evaluate open-source LLMs such as the Llama, Qwen, Mistral, and DeepSeek families. The question set currently covers more than 4690 questions across ten categories, including class definition understanding, class relation understanding, inferred relation reasoning, and other forms of structured narrative knowledge. We conduct evaluations under multiple prompting conditions, including few-shot prompting, chain-of-thought reasoning, and retrieval-augmented generation, to comprehensively test LLMs' narrative capabilities.

As an ongoing study, the work does not yet (at the time of submission) present definitive results. However, it aims to contribute two main outcomes: the first version of a growing question-answering dataset **FolkLURE** (Folklore and Literature Understanding Reasoning and Evaluation) grounded in existing fictional-domain ontologies, and an evaluation procedure for measuring LLM comprehension of literary, as well as folkloric knowledge in form of a Q&A task. With this project we aim to advance digital folkloristics and computational literary studies while also contributing to a benchmarking effort to understand how LLMs reason within constructed narrative worlds.

References

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